

The Spectrum and The Numerical Range of $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ and $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$

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Abstract: In this paper we study the spectrum and the numerical range of weighted composition operator with the adjoint of weighted composition operator $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ and $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ induced by linear α -fractional self- maps φ and ψ of \mathbb{U} on Hardy space \mathbb{H}^2 .

1. Introduction

Let \mathbb{U} denote the open unite disc in the complex plan ,let \mathbb{H}^∞ denote the collection of all holomorphic function on \mathbb{U} and let \mathbb{H}^2 is consisting of all holomorphic self-map on \mathbb{U} such that $f(z) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n z^n$ whose Maclaurin coefficients are square summable (i.e)

$f(z) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} |a_n|^2 < \infty$. More precisely $f(z) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n z^n$ if and only if $\|f\| = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} |a_n|^2 < \infty$. The inner product inducing the \mathbb{H}^2 norm is given by $\langle f, g \rangle = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n \overline{b_n}$.

Given any holomorphic self-map φ on \mathbb{U} , recall that the composition operator

is called the composition operator with symbol φ , is necessarily bounded. Let

$f \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$, the operator $T_f: \mathbb{H}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}^2$ defined by

$$T_f(h(z)) = f(z)h(z), \quad \text{for all } z \in \mathbb{U}, h \in \mathbb{H}^2$$

is called the Toeplitz operator with symbol f . Since $f \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$, then we call T_f a holomorphic Toeplitz operator. If T_f is a holomorphic Toeplitz operator, then the operator $T_f C_\varphi$ is bounded and has the form

$$T_f C_\varphi g = f(g \circ \varphi) \quad (g \in \mathbb{H}^2).$$

We call it the weighted composition operator with symbols f and φ [1] and [3], the linear operator

$$\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} g = f(g \circ \varphi) \quad (g \in \mathbb{H}^2).$$

We distinguish between the two symbols of weighted composition operator $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$, by calling f the multiplication symbol and φ composition symbol.

For given holomorphic self-maps f and φ of U , $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ is bounded operator even if $f \notin \mathbb{H}^\infty$. To see a trivial example, consider $\varphi(z) = p$ where $p \in U$ and $f \in \mathbb{H}^2$, then for all $g \in \mathbb{H}^2$, we have

$$\|\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} g\|_2 = \|g(p)\| \|f\|_2 = \|f\|_2 |\langle g, K_p \rangle| \leq \|f\|_2 \|g\|_2 \|K_p\|_2.$$

In fact, if $f \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$, then $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ is bounded operator on \mathbb{H}^2 with norm

$$\|\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}\| = \|T_f C_\varphi\| \leq \|f\|_\infty \|C_\varphi\| = \|f\|_\infty \sqrt{\frac{1+|\varphi(0)|}{1-|\varphi(0)|}}.$$

2. Basic Concepts

We start this section, by giving the following results which are collect some properties of Toeplitz and composition operators.

Lemma (2.1):[4, 6] Let φ be a holomorphic self-map of U , then

- (a) $C_\varphi T_f = T_{f \circ \varphi} C_\varphi$.
- (b) $T_g T_f = T_{gf}$.
- (c) $T_{f+\gamma g} = T_f + \gamma T_g$.
- (d) $T_f^* = T_{\bar{f}}$.

Proposition (2.2):[1] Let φ and ψ be two holomorphic self-map of U , then

1. $C_\varphi^n = C_{\varphi_n}$ for all positive integer n .
2. C_φ is the identity operator if and only if φ is the identity map.
3. $C_\varphi = C_\psi$ if and only if $\varphi = \psi$.
4. The composition operator cannot be zero operator.

For each $\alpha \in U$, the reproducing kernel at α , defined by $K_\alpha(z) = \frac{1}{1-\bar{\alpha}z}$

It is easily seen for each $\alpha \in U$ and $f \in H^2$, $f(z) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n z^n$ that

$$\langle f, K_\alpha \rangle = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n \alpha^n = f(\alpha).$$

When $\varphi(z) = (az + b)/cz + d$ is linear-fractional self-map of U , Cowen in [2] establishes $C_\varphi^* = T_g C_\sigma T_h^*$, where the Cowen auxiliary functions g , σ and h are defined as follows: $g(z) = \frac{1}{-\bar{b}z + \bar{d}}$, $\sigma(z) = \frac{\bar{a}z - \bar{c}}{-\bar{b}z + \bar{d}}$ and $h(z) = cz + d$.

If φ is linear fractional self-map U , then $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}^* = (T_f C_\varphi)^* = C_\varphi^* T_f^* = T_g C_\sigma T_h^*$.

Proposition (2.4):[5] Let each of $\varphi_1, \varphi_2, \dots, \varphi_n$ be holomorphic self-maps of U and $f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$, then

$$\mathcal{W}_{f_1, \varphi_1} \cdot \mathcal{W}_{f_2, \varphi_2} \cdots \mathcal{W}_{f_n, \varphi_n} = T_h C_\phi$$

Where $T_h = f_1 \circ (f_2 \circ \varphi_1) \circ (f_3 \circ \varphi_2 \circ \varphi_1) \circ \dots \circ (f_n \circ \varphi_{n-1} \circ \varphi_{n-2} \circ \dots \circ \varphi_1)$ and
 $C_\phi = \varphi_n \circ \varphi_{n-1} \circ \dots \circ \varphi_1$.

Corollary (2.5): Let φ be a holomorphic self-map of \mathbb{U} and $f \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$ then

$$\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}^n = T_f \circ (f \circ \varphi) \circ (f \circ \varphi_2) \circ \dots \circ (f \circ \varphi_{n-1}) \circ C_{\varphi_n}$$

The following lemma discuss the adjoint of weighted composition operator.

Lemma (2.6):[3] If the operator $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}: \mathbb{H}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}^2$ is bounded, then for each $\alpha \in \mathbb{U}$

$$\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}^* K_\alpha = \overline{f(\alpha)} K_{\varphi(\alpha)}.$$

3- The Spectrum and The Numerical Range of $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ and $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$

In this section , we consider the operators $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ and $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ induced by linear –fractional self- maps φ and ψ of \mathbb{U} . We completely characterize the shape of the spectrum and numerical rang of these operators .

Recall that [6] **the spectrum** of an operator T , denoted by $\sigma(T)$, is the set of all complex numbers λ for which $T - \lambda I$ is not invertible.

Recall that [6] **the numerical range** of an operator T on Hilbert space H is the set of complex numbers,

$$W(T) = \{ \langle Tf, f \rangle : f \in \mathcal{H}, \|f\| = 1 \}.$$

The following proposition collects some properties of the numerical range of an operator, for more details we refer the reader to [2].

Proposition (3.1):[2],[4]

- (1) $W(T)$ lies in the disc of center 0 and radius $\|T\|$.
- (2) $\sigma_p(T) \subseteq W(T)$.
- (3) $\sigma(T) \subseteq \overline{W(T)}$. ($\overline{W(T)}$ denotes the closure of $W(T)$).
- (4) If T is the identity, then $W(T) = \{1\}$. More generally , if α, β ara complex numbers , then $W(\alpha T + \beta) = \alpha W(T) + \beta$.
- (5) If T is normal operator, then $Conv \sigma(T) \subseteq \overline{W(T)}$.
 ($Conv \sigma(T)$ denotes the convex hull of $\sigma(T)$).
- (6) $W(T)$ is convex set of \mathbb{C} .
- (7) If \acute{T} is the compression of T to the closed subspace M , $W(\acute{T}) \subseteq W(T)$.

Lemma (3.2): Suppose that φ and ψ be two linear- fractional self-maps of \mathbb{U} and $f \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$. then, $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ is a weighted composition operator on Hardy space \mathbb{H}^2 .

Proof : Since each of φ and ψ is linear fractional , then put

where $a, b, c, d, a_1, b_1, c_1$ and d_1 are complex constants , such that $cz + d \neq 0$ and $c_1z + d_1 \neq 0$.

Thus , $C_\psi^* = T_g C_\sigma T_h^*$, where the Cowen auxiliary functions, g, σ and h of ψ are defined as follows :

$$g(z) = \frac{1}{-\bar{b}z + \bar{d}} , \sigma(z) = \frac{\bar{a}z - \bar{c}}{-\bar{b}z + \bar{d}} \quad \text{and} \quad h(z) = cz + d$$

Note that ,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* &= T_f C_\varphi \cdot (T_f C_\psi)^* \\ &= T_f C_\varphi C_\psi^* T_f^* \\ &= T_f C_\varphi T_g C_\sigma T_h^* T_f^* \\ &= T_f C_\varphi T_{g.[\bar{h}\bar{f} \circ \sigma]} C_\sigma \\ &= T_{f.[(g.[\bar{h}\bar{f} \circ \sigma])\varphi]} C_{\sigma \circ \varphi} \end{aligned}$$

$$= T_k C_{\sigma \circ \varphi}$$

$$= \mathcal{W}_{k,\sigma \circ \varphi}$$

$$\text{Where } k = f.[(g.[\bar{h}\bar{f} \circ \sigma])\varphi] .$$

Since each of h, f and g are in \mathbb{H}^∞ , then it is clear that $k \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$. In addition that

$$\sigma \circ \varphi = \frac{Az+B}{Cz+D} ,$$

Where $A = \bar{a}a_1 - \bar{c}c_1, B = \bar{a}b_1 - \bar{c}d_1, C = \bar{d}b_1 - \bar{b}a_1$ and $D = \bar{d}d_1 - \bar{b}b_1$.

Lemma (3.3): Suppose that φ and ψ be two linear fractional self-maps of \mathbb{U} and $f \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$, then $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ is a weighted composition operator on Hardy space \mathbb{H}^2 .

Proof : Since ψ be linear fractional , then the Cowen auxiliary functions g, σ and h are defined as above . Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} &= (T_f C_\psi)^* T_f C_\varphi \\ &= C_\psi^* T_f^* T_f C_\varphi \\ &= T_g C_\sigma T_h^* T_f^* T_f C_\varphi \\ &= T_g C_\sigma T_{\bar{h}|f|^2} C_\varphi \\ &= T_{g(\bar{h}|f|^2 \circ \sigma)} C_{\varphi \circ \sigma} \\ &= T_L C_{\varphi \circ \sigma} \end{aligned}$$

$$= \mathcal{W}_{L, \varphi \circ \sigma}$$

Where $L = g(\bar{h}|f|^2 \circ \sigma)$.

Since each of h, f and g are in \mathbb{H}^∞ , then it is clear that $L \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$. In addition that

$$\varphi \circ \sigma = \frac{A_1 z + B_1}{C_1 z + D_1} ,$$

Where $A_1 = \bar{a}a_1 - \bar{b}b_1, B_1 = \bar{d}b_1 - \bar{c}a_1, C_1 = \bar{a}c_1 - \bar{b}d_1$ and $D_1 = \bar{d}d_1 - \bar{c}c_1$. ■

We begin this section with $\mathcal{W}_{f, \varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f, \varphi}^*$ such that $\sigma \circ \varphi$ is a rational rotation of \mathbb{U} .

Remark (3.4): If $B = C = 0$ and $|A| = |D|$, then it is clear that $\sigma \circ \varphi$ is rotation . Put $(\sigma \circ \varphi)(z) = \mu z$, $\mu = A/D = e^{i\theta}$ where θ is rational number

Now, put $\mu = e^{2\pi i/n}$, where n is a positive integer number .

Suppose that j is a fixed integer number such that $0 \leq j < n$. If

$$\phi(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} a_k z^{kn+j} = z^j \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} a_k (z^n)^k = z^j \zeta(z^n)$$

where $\zeta(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} a_k z^k \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$. Note that ,

$$\begin{aligned} C_{\sigma \circ \varphi}(\phi(z)) &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} a_k ((\sigma \circ \varphi)(z))^{kn+j} \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} a_k (e^{2\pi i/n} z)^{kn+j} \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} a_k e^{2\pi i k} (e^{2\pi i/n})^j z^{kn+j} \\ &= (e^{2\pi i/n})^j \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} a_k z^{kn+j} \\ &= \mu^j \phi(z) \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Clearly μ^j is the eigenvalue of $C_{\sigma \circ \varphi}$, for each $0 \leq j < n$. Therefore, it is natural to look at the subspace H_j of functions that have such Maclaurin series. ■

Definition (3.5):[7] Let $n \geq 2$ and $0 \leq j < n$, and let H_j be the set defined by

$$H_j = \{\phi : \phi(z) = z^j \zeta(z^n) , \zeta \in \mathbb{H}^2\}.$$

It is clear that H_j is a closed subspace of \mathbb{H}^2 . Let P_j denote the orthogonal projection onto H_j .

Now, we compute the spectrum of the operator $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ where $\sigma \circ \varphi$ a rational rotation of \mathbb{U} . First we need the following lemma .

Lemma (3.6):[7] Let $n > 1$. Suppose $(z) = g(z^n)$ where $g \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$. If $0 \leq l < n$, then $\sigma(T_\psi|_{H_l}) = \overline{\psi(\mathbb{U})}$.

Theorem (3.7): Suppose that φ and ψ be two automorphism of \mathbb{U} and $f \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$. If σ is Cowen auxiliary function of ψ such that $\sigma \circ \varphi$ is a rational rotation of \mathbb{U} and $k(z) = \zeta(z^n)$ where $\zeta \in \mathbb{H}^2$, then

$$\sigma(\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*) = \overline{\bigcup_{l=0}^{n-1} \mu^l k(\mathbb{U})}$$

where $\mu = e^{2\pi i/n}$, where n is a positive integer number .

Proof : Put $T_l = T_\psi|_{H_l}$ for fixed $0 \leq l < n$. If $\phi \in H_l$, then by (1) we have $C_{\sigma \circ \varphi}(\phi) = \mu^l \phi$, and so by lemma(3.2) we get

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*(\phi) &= T_k C_{\sigma \circ \varphi}(\phi) = \mu^l k \cdot \phi \\ &= \mu^l T_l(\phi) \in H_l \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

Note that , it is easily seen that H_0, H_1, \dots, H_{n-1} are pairwise orthogonal. Put

$\mathcal{W}_l = \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*|_{H_l}$, so by (2) we have $\mathcal{W}_l = \mu^l T_l$. Thus ,

$$\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* = \mathcal{W}_0 \oplus \mathcal{W}_1 \oplus \dots \oplus \mathcal{W}_{n-1} \tag{3}$$

Hence, $\sigma(\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*) = \sigma(\mathcal{W}_0) \cup \sigma(\mathcal{W}_1) \cup \dots \cup \sigma(\mathcal{W}_{n-1})$.

Therefore, by spectral mapping theorem and lemma (3.5) we get

$$\sigma(\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*) = \overline{\bigcup_{l=0}^{n-1} \mu^l k(\mathbb{U})}. \quad \blacksquare$$

Next, we compute the numerical rang of $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ where $\sigma \circ \varphi$ is a rational rotation of \mathbb{U} . Before this , we establish the following lemma .

Lemma (3.8):[7] Let $\psi \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$. If H_j is an invariant subspace of T_ψ , then

$$W(T_\psi|_{H_j}) = \text{conv}(\psi(\mathbb{U}))$$

Theorem (3.9): Suppose that φ and ψ be two automorphism of \mathbb{U} and $f \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$. If σ is Cowen auxiliary function of ψ such that $\sigma \circ \varphi$ is a rational rotation of \mathbb{U} and $k(z) = \zeta(z^n)$ where $\zeta \in \mathbb{H}^2$, then

$$W(\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*) = \text{conv} \left(\bigcup_{l=0}^{n-1} \mu^l k(\mathbb{U}) \right)$$

where $\mu = e^{2\pi i/n}$, where n is a positive integer number .

Proof: Put $T_l = T_\psi|_{H_l}$ and $\mathcal{W}_l = \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*|_{H_l}$ for fixed $0 \leq l < n$. Thus , by (3)

we have that

$$W(\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*) = conv \left(\bigcup_{l=0}^{n-1} W(\mathcal{W}_l) \right) \quad (4)$$

If $\phi \in H_l$, then by (2) we have

$$\langle \mathcal{W}_l(\phi), \phi \rangle = \langle \mu^l T_l(\phi), \phi \rangle = \mu^l \langle T_l(\phi), \phi \rangle$$

It follows by lemma(3.8) that $W(\mathcal{W}_l) = \mu^l conv(k(U))$. Thus, by (4) we have $W(\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*) = conv(\bigcup_{l=0}^{n-1} \mu^l k(U))$. ■

Recall that $[\]$ an operator T on a Hilbert space H is called convexiod if $conv \sigma(T) = \overline{W(T)}$. Note that by proposition (3.1) (5) we have every normal operator is convexiod.

Therefore, by theorem(3.7) and (3.9) we get the following consequence.

Corollary (3.10): Suppose that φ and ψ be two automorphism of \mathbb{U} and $f \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$. If σ is Cowen auxiliary function of ψ such that $\sigma \circ \varphi$ is a rational rotation of \mathbb{U} and $k(z) = \zeta(z^n)$ where $\zeta \in \mathbb{H}^2$, then $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ is convexiod operator.

Remark (3.11): If A is a primitive n^{th} root of unity our previous results still holds in fact, if $A = e^{2\pi i m/n}$ where n and m are relatively prime and $0 \leq m < n$.

Let $\lambda = e^{2\pi i m/n}$ and $\mu = e^{2\pi i/n}$. If P_k denotes $m_j k \pmod n$, then $\lambda^{jk} = \mu^{P_k}$.

Suppose that $\phi \in H_j$, for some $0 \leq j < n$. Then, it is easily see that

$$C_{\sigma \circ \varphi}(\phi) = \mu^P \phi \text{ where } P \equiv m_j \pmod n. \text{ Then,}$$

$$\langle \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*(\phi), \phi \rangle = \langle T_k C_{\sigma \circ \varphi}(\phi), \phi \rangle = \mu^P \langle K\phi, \phi \rangle.$$

Therefore, by lemma(3.8) we have

$$W(\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* |_{H_j}) = \mu^P conv(k(U)).$$

But, $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* = \mathcal{W}_0 \oplus \mathcal{W}_1 \oplus \dots \oplus \mathcal{W}_{n-1}$ this implies that

$$W(\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*) = conv(\mu^{P_0} k(U) \cup \mu^{P_1} k(U) \cup \dots \cup \mu^{P_{n-1}} k(U)).$$

If $0 \leq j_1 < j_2 < n$, then it is easily to see that $m_{j_1} \not\equiv m_{j_2} \pmod n$ and thus

$$\{P_0, P_1, \dots, P_{n-1}\} = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1\}. \quad \blacksquare$$

In what follows we study the numerical rang of the operator $(\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*)$ where $\sigma \circ \varphi$ is an irrational rotation of \mathbb{U} , i.e. $(\sigma \circ \varphi)(z) = Az$, $A = e^{2\pi i \theta}$

such that θ is irrational number.

Lemma (3.12): Suppose that φ and ψ be two automorphism of \mathbb{U} and $f \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$. If σ is Cowen auxiliary function of ψ such that $\sigma \circ \varphi$ is an irrational rotation of \mathbb{U} and

$k(z) = 1 + \widehat{K}_1 z + \widehat{K}_2 z^2 + \dots$. Assume that n is a non-negative integer and m is a positive integer , Then $W(\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*)$ contains the ellipse with foci μ^n and μ^{n+m} whose major axis is $\sqrt{|\mu^n - \mu^{n+m}|^2 + |\widehat{K}_m|^2}$ and minor axis is $|\widehat{K}_m|$.

Proof : Let $Q = \text{span}\{e_1, e_2\}$ where $e_1(z) = z^n$ and $e_2(z) = z^{n+m}$. Then, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*(e_1)(z) &= T_k C_{\sigma \circ \varphi}(e_1)(z) \\ &= k(z) \cdot e_1(\sigma \circ \varphi(z)) \\ &= (1 + \widehat{K}_1 z + \widehat{K}_2 z^2 + \dots) A^n z^n \\ &= \mu^n z^n + \mu^n \widehat{K}_1 z^{n+1} + \mu^n \widehat{K}_2 z^{n+2} + \dots + \mu^n \widehat{K}_m z^{n+m} + \dots \end{aligned}$$

Similarly , we have

$$\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*(e_2)(z) = \mu^{n+m} z^{n+m} + \mu^{n+m} \widehat{K}_1 z^{n+m+1} + \dots$$

Thus, the matrix that represents $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ is

$$T = \begin{bmatrix} \mu^n & 0 \\ \mu^n \widehat{K}_m & \mu^{n+m} \end{bmatrix}$$

Therefore, $W(T)$ is the ellipse with foci μ^n and μ^{n+m} that described in (see[]). But $W(T) \subseteq W(\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*)$, as desired . \blacksquare

Now, we are ready to discuss the numerical rang of $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ when it is an isometry operator.

Recall that [] an operator T on Hilbert space \mathcal{H} is said to be shift operator if T is an isometry and $(T^*)^n \rightarrow 0$ strongly . Gunatillake G. in [] described the numerical range of weighted composition operator $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ when each of φ and ψ is inner function .

Lemma (3.13): Suppose that φ be a holomorphic self-map of U and $f \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$. If $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ is an isometry, then φ must be inner function and $\|f\| = 1$.

Proof : Let the operator $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ is an isometry, then $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} = I$. Thus for each $p \in U$, we have

$$\|\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} K_p\| = \|K_p\| , \text{ then } \|T_f C_\varphi K_p\| = \|K_p\|.$$

This implies that $\|f(K_p \circ \varphi)\| = \|K_p\|$. Hence , by taking $p = 0$, then $K_0 = 1$

and thus $\|f(1 \circ \varphi)\| = \|1\|$, then $\|f\| = 1$

In addition that, if $g(z) = z$, then it is clear that $\|g\| = 1$. Therefore

$$\|\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} g\| = \|g\| , \text{ and then } \|T_f C_\varphi g\| = \|g\| .$$

Thus , $\|f(g \circ \varphi)\| = \|g\|$, then $\|f \cdot \varphi\| = 1$.

Since $|\varphi(e^{it})| \leq 1 \quad a.e. \quad t \in [0, 2\pi)$

and both $\|f\|$ and $\|f \cdot \varphi\|$ are 1. Then, by the integral representation of $\|f\|_{\mathbb{H}^2}$

$$\|f\|_{\mathbb{H}^2}^2 = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} |f(e^{it})|^2 dt .$$

So that $|\varphi(e^{it})| = 1 \quad a.e. \quad on \ U$, then φ is an inner function. ■

Theorem (3.14): Let φ be an inner function that fixes the origin. If ψ is also a non-constant inner function, then $\mathcal{W}_{\psi, \varphi}$ is a shift operator such that $W(\mathcal{W}_{\psi, \varphi}) = \mathbb{U}$.

Corollary (3.15): Suppose that φ and ψ be two linear-fractional self-maps of \mathbb{U} and $f \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$ such that each of φ and σ fixes the origin, then $\mathcal{W}_{f, \varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f, \psi}^*$ is a shift operator and $W(\mathcal{W}_{f, \varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f, \psi}^*) = \mathbb{U}$.

Proof : Since $\mathcal{W}_{f, \varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f, \psi}^*$ is an isometry operator, then by lemma (3.2) and lemma (3.13) $\sigma \circ \varphi$ is an inner function and $\|k\|_\infty = 1$. But by our assumption that each of φ and σ fixes the origin, then $\sigma \circ \varphi$ is also. In addition that since $\|k\|_\infty = 1$, then we have $|k(0)| < 1$, hence k is a non-constant inner function. Therefore by theorem (3.2.13) $\mathcal{W}_{f, \varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f, \psi}^*$ is shift operator such that $W(\mathcal{W}_{f, \varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f, \psi}^*) = \mathbb{U}$. ■

Next, we study the numerical rang of $\mathcal{W}_{f, \varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f, \psi}^*$ when it is an isometry that is not unitary.

Theorem (3.16): Let $\mathcal{W}_{\psi, \varphi}$ be an isometry on \mathbb{H}^2 . If $\mathcal{W}_{\psi, \varphi}$ is not a unitary operator, then $W(\mathcal{W}_{\psi, \varphi}) = \mathbb{U} \cup \sigma_p(\mathcal{W}_{\psi, \varphi})$.

Corollary (3.17): Let φ and ψ be two linear-fractional self-maps of \mathbb{U} and $f \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$ such that either φ or ψ is not automorphism of \mathbb{U} . If $\mathcal{W}_{f, \varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f, \psi}^*$ is an isometry, then $W(\mathcal{W}_{f, \varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f, \psi}^*) = \mathbb{U} \cup \sigma_p(\mathcal{W}_{f, \varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f, \psi}^*)$.

Proof : Assume that $\mathcal{W}_{f, \varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f, \psi}^*$ is isometry operator, then by lemma(3.2) and lemma (3.13), $\|k\|_\infty = 1$. Since either φ or ψ is not automorphism of \mathbb{U} , then $\mathcal{W}_{f, \varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f, \psi}^*$ is not unitary, Therefore, by theorem(3.15) we have $W(\mathcal{W}_{f, \varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f, \psi}^*) = \mathbb{U} \cup \sigma_p(\mathcal{W}_{f, \varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f, \psi}^*)$. ■

The following result describe the spectra of unitary weighted composition operator.

Theorem (3.16): Suppose $\mathcal{W}_{\psi, \varphi}$ is unitary. If φ is elliptic with fixed point p , then $|\phi(p)| = 1$

and the spectrum of $\mathcal{W}_{\psi, \varphi}$ is the closure of the set $\{\psi(p)\phi(p)^n : n = 0, 1, 2, \dots\}$.

If φ is parabolic or hyperbolic, then the spectrum is the unit circle.

Theorem (3.19): Suppose that φ and ψ be two automorphism self-maps of \mathbb{U} and $f \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$. If $K(z) = \frac{r K_p(z)}{\|K_p\|}$ where $|r| = 1$ such that $\varphi(p) = \psi(p) = 0$, then we have the following statements :

- 1- If $\sigma \circ \varphi$ is hyperbolic or parabolic, then $W(\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*) = \mathbb{U}$.
- 2- If $\sigma \circ \varphi$ is elliptic with fixed point $p \in \mathbb{U}$. Then, if $(\sigma \circ \varphi)'(p)$ is a root of unity, we have $W(\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*) = \mathbb{U}$. Otherwise, $W(\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*)$ is a polygon with vertices $k(p), k(p).(\sigma \circ \varphi)'(p), \dots, k(p).((\sigma \circ \varphi)'(p))^{n-1}$.

Proof: Since each of φ and ψ is automorphism with above hypotheses, therefore $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ is unitary operator. Therefore, $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ is convexoid, thus

$$\text{conv } \sigma(\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*) = \overline{W(\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*)} \quad (5)$$

Therefore we can get the following cases :

(1) If $\sigma \circ \varphi$ is hyperbolic then by theorem(3.18) we have $W(\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*) = \mathbb{U}$. On the other hand, if $\sigma \circ \varphi$ is parabolic, then by theorem(3.18) we have $W(\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*) = \mathbb{U}$.

(2) If $\sigma \circ \varphi$ is elliptic with fixed point $p \in \mathbb{U}$, then by theorem(3.18) we have $|(\psi^{-1} \circ \varphi)'(p)| = 1$ and

$\sigma(\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*) = \{k(p).((\sigma \circ \varphi)'(p))^n : n = 0, 1, 2, \dots\}$. Thus two cases which are appeared

a. If $(\sigma \circ \varphi)'(p)$ is a root of unity.

$$\sigma(\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*) = \{ k(p), k(p).(\sigma \circ \varphi)'(p), \dots, k(p).((\sigma \circ \varphi)'(p))^{n-1} \}$$

Hence it is clear that by (5) we have $W(\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*)$ is a polygon with vertices $k(p), k(p).(\sigma \circ \varphi)'(p), \dots, k(p).((\sigma \circ \varphi)'(p))^{n-1}$.

b. If $(\sigma \circ \varphi)'(p)$ is not a root of unity.

Since $\|k\|_\infty = 1$, then $|k(p)| = 1$, therefore we have by [] that the set $\{k(p).(\sigma \circ \varphi)'(p)^n : n = 0, 1, 2, \dots\}$ is dense in $\sigma(\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*)$. But $(\sigma \circ \varphi)'(p)$ is not a root of unity, then $\sigma(\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*) = \partial\mathbb{U}$. This implies by (5) that $W(\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*) = \mathbb{U}$.

■

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